

THE EFFECTS OF MOISTURE ON THE SHEAR

FATIGUE OF FIBRE COMPOSITES

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Introduction

Fibre composites are being used increasingly in a diversity of engineering applications for a variety of reasons. For example the high specific strength and stiffness of carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) makes it very suitable for aerospace, while the low cost and corrosion resistance of glass fibre reinforced plastic (GRP) makes it very suitable for chemical plant.

Under quasi-static conditions the tensile strengths of unidirectional composites are very good, but under fatigue conditions although some of these materials are superior even to some high performance alloys on the basis of fatigue strength to weight ratio, some are very poor. As a rough guide, the higher the modulus of the reinforcing fibre, the better the fatigue behaviour of an un-notched unidirectional composite. This is because the stresses in the matrices of the higher modulus composites are lower than those of the lower modulus composites. Consequently high modulus carbon fibre composites display the best fatigue lives while glass fibre composites are notoriously poor in tensile fatigue.

Fibre composites are very rarely employed under conditions in which the stresses are solely tensile stresses in the fibre directions. Almost invariably shear stresses occur on planes parallel to fibres or laminae either because the composite is a multi-directional laminate, or through bending, or twisting, or stress concentrations, or a combination of these. In shear the quasi-static strengths of all composites are low on planes parallel to fibres because, as in the tensile fatigue of low modulus composites, the weakest component, the matrix or fibre-matrix interface, is highly stressed. These relatively low shear strengths are well appreciated by engineers and are accommodated in designs. It is, however, perhaps not widely appreciated how severe is the effect of shear fatigue. Recent work has demonstrated the severity of shear fatigue in the degradation of fibre composites, and this is probably potentially the most dangerous failure mode of fibre composites (1) (2) (3).

Under cyclic shear stresses, cracks initiate and propagate in the resin matrix, and it is to be expected that environmental factors which affect the matrix or fibre-matrix interface will have a significant effect

upon shear properties in general, and fatigue strengths in particular. Although the details of the processes have not been well characterised, it is now widely appreciated that during curing stresses can be induced in the resin matrix; that the absorption and desorption of water can affect these stresses by promoting swelling or shrinking; that absorbed water can affect the crack initiation and propagation characteristics of resins; and that temperature can affect all of these.

The work described in this paper has been carried out in order to obtain some comparative information about the effects of water absorption and desorption on the shear fatigue of composites containing carbon fibres, glass fibres and Kevlar fibres, both because of the engineering requirement for information of this type and because of the need to understand the processes which occur as a result of the interaction between shear fatigue stressing and the environment. Static and some fatigue measurements have been carried out on materials conditioned under ambient conditions of temperature and humidity; on specimens which had absorbed much water by soaking at 100°C; on specimens which had absorbed water and been subsequently dried; and on specimens which had been exposed to a period at 100°C in air. The results of these measurements are presented and discussed.

Experimental

Measurement of the shear properties of fibre composites is not altogether straightforward. Many techniques have been suggested but most, if not all, introduce non-shear stresses which can modify the shear characteristics. Experimentally the easiest and most widely employed method is the short beam interlaminar shear test. While this is economical and simple, and useful for quality control, for more analytical work it suffers from the disadvantages of non-uniform stresses, states of combined stress, and severe stress concentration. A more accurate but more expensive test method for unidirectional composites is the torsion technique. When a rod is twisted, shear stresses are induced on planes parallel to the rod axis, the stresses being greatest at the surface and reducing to zero at the centre. For most materials the torque-twist curve is non-linear and the shear stress varies non-linearly from the axis to the surface. Under these conditions the shear stresses can be calculated for circular section rods by a procedure due to Nadai (4). Ideally the torsion test should be carried out on thin-walled tubes, which exhibit a linear behaviour to failure and through which there is negligible shear stress variation, but for ease of fabrication and to reduce costs it is more convenient to use solid rods. Shear strengths obtained from such rods agree well with values obtained from thin-walled tubes, supporting the validity of the Nadai procedure for fibre composites (5). This technique has therefore been employed to study the fatigue of composites under low frequency cycling.

Torsion measurements were carried out on unidirectional fibre composites containing high modulus surface treated carbon fibre (CFRP), glass fibre (GRP), and Kevlar 49 fibre (KFRP). All were made by a wet lay-up technique in the form of 6 mm square section rods containing 60 volume per cent of fibre in an epoxide resin matrix, Ciba-Geigy MY750 cured with methyl nadic anhydride and benzyldimethylamine in the proportions by weight of 100:80:1, heated for 2 hours at 120°C followed by 2 hours at 180°C. Before making the KFRP specimens, the Kevlar fibre was carefully dried out at 110°C to remove absorbed moisture which can reduce adhesion of the matrix and fibres.

Torsion specimens machined from the solid rods were 150 mm long with the centre 100 mm turned down to a 6 mm diameter circular section, the 25 mm long ends being left square to enable them to be gripped in the jaws of the

testing machine. During testing, one end was held in a driven chuck and the other end was gripped in a chuck to which was attached a moment arm linked to a tension-compression load cell. Increasing torque tests were carried out to measure static shear strengths, and fatigue was carried out at ~0.17 Hz under either constant torque (+ T) or twist (+ θ) amplitude conditions at constant speed of angular rotation. During testing torque and twist were monitored continuously. The torque-twist curves of CFRP and GRP were non-linear and the maximum shear stresses were therefore calculated by the Nadai procedure. Shear modulus was calculated from the slope of the linear part of the torque-twist curves, and shear strain at failure from the angle at which cracking was detected.

Results and Discussion

Moisture Absorption

Moisture absorption of the composite materials and of cast epoxide resin was determined by measuring the weight gain of specimens soaked in demineralised water at various temperatures for several days, and some of this data is shown in Figure 1 and Table 1.

The soaked composites were torsion test pieces and the resin specimens were cylinders of 10 mm diameter x 16 mm long. Because of the differences in size, weight changes have been expressed in gm per cc of material. In addition, as the composites contained approximately 60 volume % of fibres, the epoxide resin data has been reduced by multiplying by 0.4 to give approximately the absorption that would have been expected by the equivalent amount of resin in the composites. The amount of water absorbed by CFRP and GRP at each temperature was approximately the same, and slightly less than that absorbed by the epoxide resin, probably because the resin specimens had a slightly greater surface area to volume ratio than the composite specimens. The KFRP however absorbed considerably more moisture than the epoxide resin. It is difficult to achieve a good surface finish on KFRP during machining and there is a tendency for loose fibres to protrude from the machined surface. In order to find out the effect that these fibres might have in promoting easier moisture absorption by the composite, an unmachined specimen was covered with a thin coating of resin to seal the surface. The standard deviation of absorbed mass measurements of different specimens of the same composite material was approximately +12%, and the differences between weight change of machined KFRP and unmachined KFRP coated with resin was less than this, indicating that the very considerably increased moisture absorption of KFRP over that of CFRP and GRP is an intrinsic feature of that material.

After removal from water the composites began to lose water. Figures 2 and 3 show the decrease in mass of retained water, as a function of time, of composites which had been soaked in water for several days at 100°C and were then kept in a dry environment at 22°C and 60°C. Initially there was a rapid loss of water especially at the higher temperature but it is clear that a considerable time would be required before the original, ambient-conditioned state would be achieved.

Since the objective of this work was to determine the effect on shear properties of absorbed water, and to determine the extent to which any moisture-induced changes could be restored by removing the water, the treatments described in Table 2 were arbitrarily selected for conditioning the composite materials prior to testing. "Annealed" specimens were tested in order to attempt to differentiate between effects due to moisture absorption and effects due solely to elevated temperatures. Soaked, dried and

Figure 1

Moisture absorption of the materials at 100°C

Table 1

Moisture absorbed after 7 days' immersion
in demineralised water at temperature

	Mass of water absorbed per unit volume ($10^{-2} \text{ gm cm}^{-3}$)		
	22°C	60°C	100°C
KFRP	0.5	0.7	4.8
Epoxide Resin (Equivalent amount)	0.2	0.4	1.1
GRP	0.1	0.2	0.7
CFRP	0.2	0.3	0.8

Figure 2

Moisture desorption on drying out at 22°C in air

Figure 3

Moisture desorption on drying out at 60°C in air

Table 2

Conditioning treatments for the composite materials

Title	Treatment
As-received	Stored for several weeks under ambient conditions of temperature and humidity (approx. 22°C and 55% RH)
Soaked	Immersed in demineralised water at 100°C for 7 days
Dried	Immersed in demineralised water at 100°C for 7 days followed by heating at 60°C in dry air for 7 days
Annealed	Stored in dry air at 100°C for 7 days

annealed specimens were placed on test within an hour of removal from the conditioning treatment.

Shear Fatigue of As-Received Composites

Typical torque-twist curves for the three composite materials, after conditioning at ambient temperature and humidity, are shown in Figure 4, and Table 3 contains shear strengths, moduli and strains at failure. The shear properties of the GRP and CFRP were a good deal higher than those of the KFRP and their torque-twist curves became non-linear before failure while that of the KFRP was elastic to failure. Fatigue has been studied under both constant angular amplitude (constant shear strain) and constant torque amplitude (constant shear stress) conditions. The behaviour of all three composite systems is similar, and Figures 5 and 6 show the behaviour of unidirectional GRP and CFRP respectively in these cycling modes. Under constant shear strain amplitude conditions, torque or shear stress progressively decrease as the compliance increases. Initially this decrease is linear with log (no. of cycles) until macroscopic cracks are initiated, often audibly, and propagate along the specimen. The knees on the curves in Figure 5 thus define the fatigue life of the material and a plot of fatigue life against shear strain amplitude is shown in Figure 7. Although the scatter is quite large, so that it is not possible to be certain about the shape of this S-N curve, it is convenient to fit a straight line to the points as shown, and Figure 8 shows combined data for the three composites and epoxide resin. Similar behaviour occurs under constant shear stress amplitude conditions, the increase in compliance leading to an increase in strain amplitude as shown in Figure 6. The behaviour of unreinforced resin during shear cycling is quite different, inasmuch as there is no change in compliance during cycling until cracking occurs, so that the behaviour in constant shear stress cycling is identical to constant shear strain cycling. This, and other indirect evidence, has led to the suggestion that the initial increase in compliance of composites prior to cracking is due at least partially to debonding (3). The slope of the torque versus log N curve, during this debonding stage, increases with increasing strain amplitude and figure 9 shows $\Delta T/\log N$ as a function of strain amplitude.

FIGURE 4

Torque-twist behaviour of the as-received composites

Table 3

Static shear properties of the composite materials after conditioning

Material	Treatment	Shear Strength MNm ⁻²	Shear Modulus GNm ⁻²	Shear Strain (x 10 ⁻³)
CFRP	As-received	76 ± 9 (8)	3.5 ± 0.6 (8)	39 ± 11 (8)
	Soaked	61 ± 6 (4)	3.4 ± 0.2 (4)	25 ± 10 (4)
	Dried	72 ± 9 (4)	3.5 ± 0.2 (4)	29 ± 4 (4)
	Annealed	81 ± 13 (4)	3.7 ± 0.6 (4)	37 ± 11 (4)
GRP	As-received	79 ± 3 (5)	3.8 ± 0.2 (3)	67 ± 4 (5)
	Soaked	55 ± 6 (4)	4.3 ± 0.2 (4)	40 ± 8 (4)
	Dried	63 ± 7 (4)	4.0 ± 0.4 (3)	31 ± 4 (4)
	Annealed	82 ± 2 (3)	3.5 ± 0.3 (3)	37 ± 4 (3)
KFRP	As-received	48 ± 4 (6)	1.5 ± 0.1 (6)	27 ± 3 (6)
	Soaked	27 ± 2 (4)	1.4 ± 0.3 (4)	34 ± 1 (4)
	Dried	33 ± 2 (3)	1.3 ± 0.1 (4)	31 ± 5 (4)
	Annealed	34 ± 2 (4)	1.4 ± 0.1 (4)	27 ± 1 (3)

Uncertainties are standard deviations

Figures in brackets are the number of specimens

Figure 5

Variation of torque amplitude under constant angular amplitude cycling
As-Received GRP

Figure 6

Variation of angular amplitude during constant torque amplitude cycling
As-Received CFRP

Figure 7

Fatigue lives of as-received CFRP under constant strain amplitude cycling

Figure 8

Fatigue lives of all the materials in the as-received condition under constant strain amplitude cycling. CFRP I and CFRP II are high modulus and high strength CFRP

Figure 9

The rate of decrease of torque during constant strain amplitude cycling, prior to cracking, as-received composites

Shear Fatigue of Soaked, Dried and Annealed Composites

The quasi-static shear properties of the composite materials after the various conditioning treatments are shown in Table 3. The relatively small number of specimens tested makes any conclusions somewhat uncertain, but some interesting features appear to be emerging.

The effect of soaking was to reduce the shear strength of each material significantly. In the case of KFRP which absorbed seven times more water than GRP and CFRP the strength was reduced to a half. The failure strains of CFRP and GRP were also considerably reduced, by an amount proportionately more than the shear strengths, while the failure strain of KFRP was, if anything, slightly increased. The differences in shear moduli resulting from soaking were probably not significant.

On drying, all the shear strengths recovered at least partially towards their original values. The recovery of CFRP was almost complete but there was a significant shortfall with GRP and a very large shortfall with KFRP. From Figure 3 it will be appreciated that KFRP retains a good deal of water after the drying treatment and that CFRP and GRP retain an almost equal but smaller amount. Drying did not cause a significant recovery of the failure strain of GRP and CFRP, and these remained substantially lower than in the as-received condition. The failure strain of KFRP was not significantly affected by drying. The shear moduli of the three systems were not significantly affected by drying.

On annealing, the shear strengths of CFRP and KFRP were, if anything, slightly increased, although the increase may not be significant, while the shear strength of KFRP was decreased. Annealing had no effect on the failure strain of CFRP and KFRP but significantly reduced that of GRP. The effect of annealing on shear modulus was probably not significant.

Shear fatigue measurements have been carried out under constant angular amplitude (constant shear strain) conditions on soaked specimens and dried specimens. The most obvious effect of soaking was to soften the line of the curve of torque amplitude versus log (No. of cycles) as shown in Figure 10. Instead of the relatively sharp change in slope that occurred in the as-received material, as shown in Figure 5 for GRP, the change in slope was more gradual, the point at which macroscopic cracking occurred was less precise, and the initial rate of growth of shear cracks beyond this point appeared to be reduced. On drying, the shapes of the curves recovered towards the shapes of the curves of as-received specimens as shown in Figure 11. Flattening of the curves on soaking was most pronounced for KFRP and recovery to the original shape was least effective on drying; for CFRP the effect was least and recovery was most complete; while for GRP the effect was intermediate between that of KFRP and CFRP.

The effect of soaking and drying on the fatigue lives of the materials during constant angular amplitude cycling is shown in Figures 12, 13 and 14. The more extensive data that has been collected for as-received composites of CFRP and published elsewhere (3) has shown that a straight line may be fitted to fatigue data of this type. Accordingly lines have been fitted to the data in Figures 12 to 14 to indicate more clearly the trends of behaviour. It is clear from these graphs that the effect of soaking CFRP and GRP is to reduce the fatigue lives at all shear strain amplitudes, and that drying does not produce any significant recovery in this cycling mode despite the fact that static shear strengths are almost completely recovered. The behaviour of KFRP is quite different. Although this material absorbed the most water, lost the greatest proportion of its static shear strength, and failed to recover its strength very significantly on drying, these

Figure 10

Variation of torque amplitude under constant angular amplitude cycling
Soaked GRP

Figure 11

Variation of torque amplitude under constant angular amplitude cycling
Dried GRP

Figure 12

Fatigue lives of CFRP under constant shear strain amplitude cycling after various treatments

Figure 13

Fatigue lives of GRP under constant shear strain amplitude cycling after various treatments

Figure 14

Fatigue lives of KFRP under constant shear strain amplitude cycling after various treatments

treatments have no significant effects on fatigue lives under constant shear strain amplitude cycling.

The effects of conditioning on the initial slopes of the torque versus log N curves, prior to cracking, are shown in Figures 15, 16 and 17. For CFRP the treatments have no distinguishable effect on the rate of increase of compliance, or the strain amplitude below which compliance would not be expected to change. For GRP, soaking increases the rate of change at all strain amplitudes but this effect is somewhat recovered on drying. There also appears to be a decrease in the critical shear strain amplitude at which compliance changes would be expected. For KFRP soaking also increases the rate of change but drying, if anything, appears to further increase it and to decrease the strain amplitude at which changes begin to occur.

Any discussion of these phenomena must necessarily be speculative at this stage in view of the limited amount of data and absence of supporting studies. It is interesting that for CFRP the debonding behaviour, as illustrated by Figure 15, is not affected by soaking, while the fatigue life is. The opposite is true for KFRP where debonding is largely dependent on moisture and environment, and the fatigue life is not. Only for GRP are both the fatigue life and the debonding behaviour both affected by moisture.

Water absorption will plasticise the matrix, increasing its toughness and deformability, and cause it to swell. It will also affect the Kevlar fibres, promoting their swelling, and affecting the fibre-matrix interface. These two last effects will modify the composites in different ways. Further, the stresses frozen into the composites during fabrication will be different because of the different thermal expansions of the fibres, and the swelling of the matrix will result in changes in these frozen-in stresses. Hence there is no reason to suppose a priori that the behaviour of the three composite materials will be the same on soaking and drying, nor that the same explanation can be used for the different effects in each.

The features common to all three composites are the loss of shear strength and softening of the line of the fatigue curves on soaking, and their partial recovery on drying. Swelling of the matrix would be expected to increase its grip on the fibres and thus by improving the fibre-matrix bond, to increase shear strength. That it does not, is probably due to a

Figure 15

$\Delta T/\log N$ during constant strain amplitude cycling of CFRP

Figure 16

$\Delta T/\log N$ during constant strain amplitude cycling of GRP

Figure 17

$\Delta T / \log N$ during constant strain amplitude cycling of KFRP

reduction in yield strength and ultimate failure stress of the matrix. In fatigue, failure of the soaked specimen tends to occur at lower strains and thus with lower stored elastic energy available to propagate the cracks. This, combined with the increased toughness of the matrix, reduces the severity of the initial crack growth stage.

CFRP and GRP absorb similar amounts of water on soaking, and desorb similar amounts on drying, but the effect on the shear strength of GRP is slightly greater and its recovery is less. A possible explanation of this is loss of the silane coupling of glass fibres. When E glass fibres are immersed in boiling demineralised water, a small amount of the glass surface is lost into solution. It is possible that this effect occurred in the composite leading to a permanent fall in strength.

Conclusion

To summarise the principal conclusions which may be drawn from this work:

- Kevlar fibre composites absorb considerably more water than can be attributed to the resin alone, while moisture absorption of CFRP and GRP is approximately the same as that of the equivalent amount of resin.
- Absorbed water causes significant decreases in static shear strength, the large amount of moisture absorbed by KFRP reducing its shear strength to approximately a half of as-received material. Absorbed water also reduces the shear strain to failure of CFRP and GRP and the effect is greater than for shear strength, but there is no significant decrease for KFRP.
- Drying causes partial recovery of shear strength of all the composites but little or no recovery of strain to failure of GRP and CFRP. The strain to failure of KFRP is unaffected by either soaking or drying.

- . Under constant shear strain cycling (constant angular amplitude) there is a reduction of fatigue life of CFRP and GRP at all amplitudes on soaking and no evidence of a recovery on drying. Soaking and drying have no effect on the fatigue life of KFRP.
- . The rate of change of compliance prior to cracking which has been measured in terms of Δ Torque/log N, and has been associated with debonding (3), is unaffected by soaking and drying of CFRP. It is increased by soaking GRP and partially recovered by drying. It is increased by soaking KFRP and may increase on drying.

Further work is required to determine the general validity of these conclusions and to extend the study to the behaviour of cross-plyed laminates under shear stressing.

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